

Linguistics and its branches

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Abstract: This article looks into different aspects of linguistics, a science that studies the role of language in personal life. We take a brief look at the structure of language and the broader interdisciplinary branches of linguistics that anyone interested in the study of languages needs to know about.

Keywords: Linguistics, structure, practical and theoretical form, historical development, general linguistics, communication, function, classifications, development of linguistics, typological linguistics, the formation of language.

Linguistics is the study of language in general. Linguistics is based on practical and theoretical forms, and theoretical linguistics studies the structure (grammar) of languages and their semantics. Grammar-morphology (the structure and changes of your structure) includes the sciences of syntax (the way words and sentences are combined) and phonology (learning with sounds).

Applied linguistics, on the other hand, deals with the practical application of what has been learned in the theoretical part of linguistics. Applied linguistics includes subjects such as translation, speech therapy, pathology, and language learning.

Linguistics is the study of the social nature, function, internal structure, classification, laws of language, and its historical development. Depending on the purpose and function, there are several areas of language: general linguistics - the study of human language phenomena, practical linguistics - the development of methods for solving problems related to the use of language (phonetics, transcription, lexicography).

The word linguistics is widely used in several European countries: English, French, Spanish, Russian and other languages, and the word linguistics is based on "lingua" and it means "tongue". An other alternative translation of linguistics in Uzbek, "linguistics," is a synonymous relationship.

In the science of linguistics or linguistics, a whole object is studied as a complex social communication tool. Linguistics is symbol of spirituality, which appears in various forms in the study of the language, which is the wealth of the nation.

Linguistics is an extremely powerful symbol of spirituality, manifested in the following forms in the process of learning a language that is the wealth of the nation:

1. Dynamic Linguistics, Dynamic Linguistics mainly studies language in its real existence, in the active performance of various tasks, in “development”, in change.

2. Static linguistics. Static linguistics distinguishes and describes a specific period (segment) in language development that is fully synchronized. This field of linguistics, in contrast to dynamic linguistics, is completely excluded from the process of development and change in language, without approaching it, examines the state of the language - a certain "stagnant" part of the modern period.

3. Atomistic linguistics. Atomic linguistics focuses on the study of the development and growth of each individual language unit.

4. Structural linguistics. Structural linguistics examines the internal relationships and connections in a language system.

He studies the natural, necessary interrelationships between the structural layers of the language system (phonetic, lexical, morphological, syntactic, tably, necessary bogfighter levels).

5. Synchronous linguistics. Synchronous linguistics is an integral part of static and structural linguistics, serving to describe the "stagnant", "varied" state of a language in a given period.

6. Diachronic linguistics. Diachronic linguistics is an integral part of dynamic and atomistic linguistics, which studies the laws and consequences of the development of language and the development of language units.

7. Intralinguistics (internal linguistics). Internal linguistics studies the systematic relationship of language units, regardless of extralinguistic factors. The research source of internal linguistics is phonology, lexicology and grammar.

8. Extralinguistics (external linguistics). Foreign linguistics studies the development and function of language in abundance with factors such as socio-political, socio-historical, ethnic, geographical. Accordingly, this linguistics examines language as a social phenomenon.

9. Macrolinguistics. Macrolinguistics takes language in a wide range, “on a large scale,” and studies it on the basis of statistical methods. Clearly, this field analyzes language through statistical methods. Z methods, analysis by statistical methods

10 Microlinguistics. Microlinguistics is part of the language system (structure) studies relationships, interactions, and contradictions.

11. Paralinguistics. Paralinguistics is rich in direct speech activity, in which hand and facial movements (gestures, facial expressions), which occur simultaneously with the expression of ideas in the speech process, are a constant companion of spoken speech, the height of speech, depressive-emotional bo. ‘is an area that explores a number of aspects, such as expressive-emotional paint.

12. Psycholinguistics. Psycholinguistics as a generalization (synthesis) of the sciences of psychology and linguistics studies the speech process in terms of content, communicative significance, the fact that the act of speech is directed to a specific socio-practical goal, in accordance with it. He pays special attention to the unity of form and content in the expression of thought in speech.

In general, language learning is a coherent and complex process that involves a complete study of the events that take place in a language, the influence of that language on another language, and the culture and history of those who communicate in that language. Each language is a historically formed, widely used, and universal means of communication.

The term "linguistics" is the most widely used, and linguistics is internationally comprehensive. Linguistics is the study of the social nature, purpose, functions, and structure of language; and the activity of language is about individual languages, their laws, historical processes, and general classification.

Linguistics as a science is divided into two parts: general and special. The main task of private linguistics is to compare dissimilar languages, and in this case typological linguistics is distinguished. Private linguistics is the study of individual languages, including psychology - the study of Russian, Ukrainian studies - the study of Ukrainian, and so on. Private linguistics should be studied synchronously (study of existing facts in language) and diachronically (study of parts of language development). In addition, private linguistics deals with the structural features and processes of a particular language or group of languages.

Theoretical Linguistics - Theoretical study of language is the generalization of information. Serves as part of applied linguistics. Applied Linguistics is the study of linguistics (related to technology) used in modern life to deal with practical problems encountered in the study of language and the practical application of linguistics in other fields. The first stage of development of linguistics as a science was in the VI-XVIII centuries BC. Problems in linguistics have arisen, linguistics has become the basis of terminology, and basic manuals for studying different languages of the world have been collected.

Problems with language learning have long been a concern for scholars and thinkers. The formation of language, the processes of its development, and the promotion of its widespread use have been studied for a long time, and it is still being repeated.

The place and role of language in society and in our human society as a whole is of great importance, as it allows us to study the events that take place in it and to communicate with other sciences.

Therefore, modern linguistics is studied as a multidisciplinary linguistics that is closely related to the study of modern knowledge and in almost all fields. Linguistics also serves as a foundation for communicating ideas in a variety of ways, developing creative thinking, thinking, language structure, identity, distinction from existing languages, worldviews, national pride, and ideological immunity.

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